

Hepatitis B and C and the use of biosecurity measures by manicures and pedicures of the city of Maceió, Brazil

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ABSTRACT Background: Hepatitis B and C can be transmitted in beauty salons, through the use and sharing of materials with sharp objects. **Methods:** This cross-sectional study was conducted as part of an ongoing trial to assess the seroepidemiological profile (for hepatitis B and C) in manicures and pedicures (n = 30) from salons of the city of Maceió, Brazil. Moreover assess their knowledge about these diseases and biosecurity practices used (Ethical Review number,175261138.00000039). **Results:** The results showed that 60% of the participants were between 26 and 40 years of age; among these, 65% say having done vocational college and 53.34% completed high school. Concerning the research of hepatitis B and C in these individuals, have not been found serological markers for these viruses in no professional evaluated. About vaccination status, only 50% of volunteers vaccinated for hepatitis B were immunized. With respect to the transmission of these diseases, 70% of individuals did not know about this. On Biosafety assessment, 80% were not sterilisation process control, and 50% of them used personal protective equipment. **Conclusion:** It can be concluded that these professionals need to be made aware of biosecurity for the professional exercise and the importance of immunisation and examination of anti-HBS as a form of prevention for hepatitis B.

KEYWORDS Hepatitis, Manicures, Biosafety

Introduction

Hepatitis is an inflammation of the liver that can be caused by viruses, alcohol, use of certain medications, some types of drugs, besides autoimmune metabolic and genetic diseases[1].

Various etiological agents cause viral hepatitis. Despite the similarity between the different types of hepatitis from the clinical and laboratory point of view, they differ for the kind of virus, its evolution and epidemiology[2]. There are at least seven types of viral agents involved in the genesis of hepatitis, and

they are classified into A, B, C, D, E, G and TT. These viruses have hepatotropic in common, but they present characteristics that distinguish them, for example, the capability to determine chronic and systemic infections, typing A and B, most of the times, the responsible for the acute forms of infection[3].

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) infection is a significant public health problem worldwide and one of the major causes of chronic, professional carrier conditioning, as it is not advisable to continue your professional practice[4].

Hepatitis B virus (HBV) is classified in the HepaDNA family. Because of its high specificity, the HBV infects humans, making them natural reservoirs[5]. The transmission of the hepatitis B virus happens through the solution of continuity (skin and mucosa); sexual relations; percutaneous exposures (parenteral), or other contaminated instruments exposure[6].

HCV belongs to the genus Hepacivirus of the Flaviviridae family. The VHC transmission occurs by percutaneous exposures to blood, by use of injecting drugs and blood transfusions, but it can also be transmitted through sex with an infected partner, though this kind of transmission is less frequent[7].

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The virus of hepatitis C has as its characteristic a long-term infection with the absence of symptoms, causing severe complications to the patient, such as liver cirrhosis and liver cancer[8]. It is estimated that approximately 350 million people worldwide are infected with hepatitis B and 170 million people are infected with hepatitis C virus[9]. There is a severe problem concerning the transmission of VHB and VHC, which is the reckless way work to prevent infections in the workplace since the risk of contamination is proportional to the exposure to this viral particles[10].

The number of beauty institutions in Brazil is quite significant. Manicures and pedicures are workers who take care of the beauty of hands and feet. Its activities bring great concern to public health since bleeding from the habit of removing nail cuticles without adequate sterilisation of the instruments can be an essential disseminator of these viral agents[11].

This study aimed at identifying the degree of knowledge of these professionals regarding hepatitis forms of transmission, as well as to assess the level of contamination by these viruses, the immunisation and the vaccine response.

Methods

The type of study conducted in this survey was the cross-sectional, having been submitted to the Committee for Ethics in Research and Education from University Center Cesmac with the following Presentation Certificate for Ethical Review number (PCER): 175261138.00000039 and with approval obtained on August 07, 2013.

Thirty (30) manicures and / or pedicure were assessed, aged 18 or older, who worked in beauty salons in the city of Maceió, Brazil, and who showed interest in participating in the study through the signature of the Informed Consent Form (ICF). After obtaining the signature of ICF, manicures and pedicures were asked to answer a questionnaire containing open and closed questions on knowledge of bloodborne diseases, especially hepatitis B and C, as well as about the biosafety procedures used in their day-to-day professional routine following modifications in the questionnaire used by Cortelli[12].

Collection of blood samples

Blood samples were obtained by venous puncture using tubes for vacuum collection, with gel separator and capacity of 8 ml of blood. For the packaging and transportation of these samples, a thermal box with recyclable ice was used. This material was subsequently forwarded to Lufer Laboratory for carrying out the immunology assays related to the diagnosis of hepatitis B and C and assessment of vaccine response in individuals who had already been immunised against hepatitis B.

Diagnosis of Hepatitis B

To verify the presence of hepatitis B surface antigen, it was used the Doles® company commercial kit that uses the immunochromatographic method.

Diagnosis of hepatitis C

For the diagnosis of hepatitis C, it was used a system for a rapid and qualitative determination of specific IgG antibodies against the hepatitis C virus in serum samples from individuals participating in the study. The methodology used for this evaluation is based on immunochromatography. The kit used was by Doles® company.

Graph 1: Distribution of the age range of the individuals interviewed.

Graph 2: Level of education of the professionals interviewed.

Evaluation of vaccine response in immunised individuals

The immune status of healthcare professionals was determined by qualitative and quantitative analysis of the level of antibodies against the hepatitis B surface antigen (anti-HBsAg). The kit used for the individual immunity confirmation was Doles® company.

Results and Discussion

This research was conducted in the city of Maceió, Brazil, in eight beauty salons grouped in six distinct neighbourhoods (Ponta Verde, Jatiúca, Bom Parto, Farol, Jacintinho and Mangabeiras). The visits to these establishments were not pre-scheduled and were conducted informally, where a semi-structured questionnaire was applied addressing issues related to professional training, biosafety, hygiene notions and prevention of blood contact-transmissible diseases.

All of the 30 professionals interviewed, worked as manicures and pedicures, 93.3% of which were female and only 6.7% male, thus showing the female prevalence in this work segment. These results are different from those found by Garbaccio and Oliveira[13] who also evaluated manicures and / or pedicures working in beauty salons. These researchers found that out of the 84 his survey participants, all were female, similar to the results found by Cordeiro, Hemmi and Ribeiro[14], who conducted a program in health and education with manicures and pedicures in the city of Diamantina, MG, with a total of 26 participants, 100% of them being female.

Graph 3: Knowledge of blood-borne diseases.

Graph 4: Percentage of handwashing of the professionals during their activity.

However, the results obtained by Moraes et al.[15] in a survey on the knowledge the beauty professionals had about the risks and adoption of biosecurity measures against infection of hepatitis B in Itauna, MG resembles those of the present work, with 98.4% of volunteers belonging to the female sex.

About age, it was observed in the present study, a higher prevalence (60%) between the ages of 26 and 40, as shown in Graph 1. This result is by the one found by Garbaccio and Oliveira[14] in which the prevalent age in the group of 54 manicures varied between 18-24 years old (27.8%) and 37-42 years old (27.8%), with a mean age of 33.4 years old.

These results are also equivalent to those obtained by Yoshida et al.[16], in a survey regarding sterilisation process of instruments in shops offering manicure and pedicure services, where the average age of participants was 33.8 years. In a paper on biosafety procedures adopted by beauty professionals in the city of Jacareí-SP, conducted by the Cortelli[12], it was observed that 62.55% of respondents were between 26 and 40 years old, thus characterising a higher prevalence of these professionals (manicures and pedicures) within this age range.

It was found that 65% of respondents attended vocational courses to develop their activities, while 35% did their work without receiving any qualification. In the study conducted by Cortelli[12] it was detected that only 55% of them were trained to exercise the profession. On the opposite, Yoshida and t al.[16] found that 72% of the employees were qualified for that.

About education, Graph 2 shows that the vast majority, 53.34%, finished high school.

Oliveira, Prisciele and Mamfredini[17] described similar results on the degree of information of the manicures and pedicures of Uruguaiana-RS concerning hepatitis B and C, where the majority affirmed to have finished high school.

Besides having primary education, knowledge on the part of these workers on blood-borne diseases and prevention during their working activities is of great importance. The percentage

Graph 5: Sterilization equipment used by the manicure's pedicures interviewed.

Graph 6: Percentage of vaccinated and immunized individuals.

represented in Graph 3 reflects that the vast majority (86.6%) is aware that they can transmit some disease.

However, this study found that as for the understanding of pathologies, 100% of them had knowledge of AIDS, but 33.35% had no clue what hepatitis meant, as it can be seen in Graph 3. About science on the way hepatitis is transmitted, 70% said they did not have such information. These results differ from those found by Moraes et al.[15] who analysed the perception of risk contamination through the virus of hepatitis B and the adoption of biosecurity measures by manicures in Itaúna - MG and observed that 79.5% of the volunteers in his survey were aware of how blood-borne diseases are transmitted. However, in a study conducted in São Paulo by Oliveira[18], it was observed that 85% of the interviewees knew how hepatitis C is transmitted.

Among the individuals assessed, it was reported that 50% of them did not wear individual protection equipment (IPes) during their professional activities. This result differs from the one found by Moraes et al.[15], where it was observed that only 12.6% of the professionals evaluated did not make use of gloves. In this present study, 93.3% of the volunteers declared they had already been exposed to customers' blood at some point during their professional lives. These results are higher and differ from those found in a study about prevention and diagnosis of hepatitis C, carried out by Diniz and Matte[19], where only 45% of the respondents reported this fact.

The results of this research also differ from those obtained in a study on the prevention and diagnosis of hepatitis C, carried out by Oliver et al.[20] with manicures in Alfenas-MG, where 50% of them said they had already been through this type of incident.

Beauty salons propose offering a welfare, embellishment and relaxation area. Thus, the activities developed are directly linked to body contact and for this reason, controlling the transmission

Table 1: Biosafety cautions followed by the manicures and pedicures interviewed.

Home	YES	NO
Do you know what instrument sterilization is?	96.7%	3.3%
Are single-use materials (hair removal blade, nail pick, nail files etc.) scrapped after being used?	76.7%	23.3%
Are there soap liquid and disposable towel for hand hygiene compliance of the professionals?	73.3%	26.7%
Is there alcohol gel to sanitize the professionals' hands?	86.7%	13.3%
Do you pre-disinfect the instruments by immersing them in an appropriate solution?	73.3%	26.7%
Do you perform biological or chemical control of the sterilization process?	20%	80%
Do you use enclosures and / or box identified with sterilization and expiration date?	0%	100%
Is there a written routine of the sterilization process?	0%	100%
Is there rigid container for disposal of needles and sharps?	20%	80%
Do you have instruments (scissors and nail pliers) in sufficient quantity to ensure sterilization after each use?	93.3%	6.7%

Table 2: Methods of use of equipment for the sterilization of the materials used by the beauty professionals interviewed.

Time and temperature of use to equipment sterilization	Percentage
Oven (120 ° C - 60 min)	1 6,67 %
Oven (250 ° C - 60 min)	25 %
Autoclave (180 ° C - 30 min)	25 %
Autoclave (180 ° C - 60 min)	20, 83 %
Autoclave (145 ° C - 60min)	12.5 %

of infectious diseases is essential. The biosafety care of the individuals evaluated during the daily practice of their activities is described in Table 1.

As it can be seen in Graph 4, in this work it was also detected that 60% of the individuals always had the habit of washing their hands before start serving each customer, while 20% reported carrying this procedure only occasionally. However, the most alarming fact was that 20% of the participants reported they have never carried this protocol out, differing from the data of the survey conducted by Moraes et al.[15] with 127 manicures of beauty salons, where it was found that 72.4% of professionals had this habit as a standard procedure.

About the equipment used for sterilisation, Diniz and Matté,[19] noticed that 57.5% had inadequate equipment. These results differ from the present research, which found that 20% of the establishments made use of equipment commonly known as "little ovens" (Graph 5).

According to what was showed in Graph 5, 80% of manicures /pedicures surveyed used the oven or autoclave, which are considered an appropriate device for sterilization of the instruments

Table 3: Time of professional practice as manicures and pedicures.

Time of profession	Percentage
<1 year	0%
From 1 to 2 years	6.66%
From 3 to 5 years	23.34%
From 6 to 10 years	23.34%
> 10 years	46.66%

used. Nevertheless, out of this percentage, according to the responses obtained by the respondents, all of them followed sterilization procedure incorrectly, as it can be seen in Table 2. It is worth mentioning that some techniques used by these individuals and presented below reach the goal of successful sterilisation, though there is unnecessary waste of energy and time.

Another critical point observed in the present research was that employees from the same beauty salon claimed to use two different procedures for the sterilization of the instruments, which reinforces the need for training these professionals.

Moraes et al.[15] studies revealed that 83% of the participants made use of ovens, but 98.9% of them did not handle them properly, while 11.3% used the autoclave and 5.7% utilised other methods.

In addition to the use of biosecurity procedures, in this study it was also evaluated the vaccine status of the professionals in this working area, where it was detected that 53,3% of them were vaccinated against hepatitis B. However, only 50% of these individuals were actually immunised. This low number shows that the completion of immunization procedure does not fully guarantee against hepatitis B infection, becoming necessary to perform an anti-HBs test to obtain certainty regarding immune protection.

The anti-HBs is a marker of hepatitis B serologic immunity. Individuals vaccinated, as well as people who had the disease present this serologic marker. There are cases in which in spite of having entirely administered the three doses, the individual still needs to repeat the vaccination plan to ensure immune protection. Therefore, it is essential to carry out vaccination to check the immunity[21].

Regarding the tests to detect infection by the viruses of hepatitis B and C, no serological markers were found for these viruses in any of the beauty professionals evaluated, differing from the study by Oliveira[18] with 100 manicures and / or pedicures in beauty salons in the city of São Paulo, where 10% of the assessed individuals presented positive results, being 8% for hepatitis B and 2% for hepatitis C.

Regarding the time of professional activity, 46.66% of the volunteers participating in this study have been working in this field for more than ten years as it can be seen in Table 3.

Conclusion

According to the data obtained in this research, it can be concluded that manicures and pedicures working in the beauty salons of the city of Maceio, AL must be made aware of the need to use SEs while exercising their profession. Another important point, still on the issue of biosafety is related to training these professionals so they can follow the necessary proceedings for proper sterilisation of the instruments.

Regarding vaccination for hepatitis B, a small index of these professionals were immunised, requiring an active campaign to shed light on the importance of immunisation and the realisation of anti-HBs test as a prevention of this disease.

Competing Interests

There were no financial supports or relationships between authors and any organization or professional bodies that could pose any conflict of interest.

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